
METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING SOLUTION OF GRAPHIC PROBLEMS

Mammadli Ch.

ASPU physics faculty teacher

Mansurova L.

ASPU physics faculty teacher

ABSTRACT

The methodology of teaching graphic problems in physics focuses on the importance of graphing as a tool for visualizing and understanding physical phenomena. Graphs are used to depict the relationship between variables, such as time and position, velocity, or acceleration, providing insights into the behavior of physical systems. The primary goal is to teach students how to interpret, construct, and use graphs effectively to solve problems and analyze the relationship between physical quantities. A graph is a visual representation that shows the relationship between different variables, often using lines or curves. In physics, graphs help to represent functions, such as the relationship between displacement and time, or velocity and time. These relationships can describe various types of motion, including uniform motion (constant velocity) and accelerated motion (uniform or non-uniform acceleration).

Keywords: methodology, graphic, graph showing, physics problems.

There are different ideas about the concept of graphics. A graphic is a visually visible drawing with the help of lines and other graphic elements. A graph is a visual representation of the relationship between numbers and quantities in mathematics. In mathematics, the concept of graph and functional dependence is introduced, but the qualitative analysis of graphs is not considered.

It is necessary to train the students to show the relationship between the quantities characterizing the event. A graph showing the change of a quantity is an additional way to express the relationship between two dependent quantities in addition to a long description or formula given in words. When you skillfully use the graphical method, it becomes more visual, allows you to grasp the various stages of the studied phenomenon at a glance and quickly find one or another of its specific values on the graph of its functions.

Therefore, many problems of the course, including all laboratory work showing the dependence between two quantities, should end with graphing. Graphs are often used in solving problems in physics. By taking measurements on the graph, you can get an idea about the progress of the process. This visualization allows the physical regularities given in the problem condition to be better understood or the analytical calculation to be simplified. For example, a graph showing the change of the route depending on time; a graph showing the change in temperature of a solid body as a function of time when it is heated; a graph showing the pressure dependence of the volume of the same gas mass at a constant temperature; a graph showing the temperature dependence of the saturated vapor pressure; graphs showing the dependence of the current intensity on the resistance, the dependence of the deformation on the elastic force, etc.

In the training process, in addition to the graphs drawn by students individually, it is possible to prepare many graphs (energy distribution in the solar spectrum) in the form of wall charts. Students can also draw such graphs. These charts are hung on the classroom wall or on the blackboard during the lesson to help the teacher. Since it is necessary to widely use graphs during the quantitative experiments carried out in the classroom

and when solving the problem, there should be a second board in the classroom with an area of not less than 1m² and divided into square decimeters by a colored line, and the graphs should be drawn on this board (the functions of the smart board can also be used).

10-20% of physics problems are graphical problems. Therefore, it is necessary to teach students to "read" the graph. So what does that mean? The student should determine: the type of movement described in the graph, the initial and final values of the variable quantity, the meeting place, to perform calculations based on the data to find the physical quantity, etc.

Graphic representation can be used in the consolidation, development and application of knowledge. Graphical tasks and problems can be divided into several groups: graphical tasks, problem solving by graphical method and graphical representation of measurement results. Each of them is used for a specific purpose. It is impossible to say exactly where, in which part of the course, in the teaching of which events this or other group of tasks and issues will be used.

The physical content itself determines their place in the general physics course. In the lesson, depending on the goal, the teacher can choose an arbitrary type of problem. Graphical problems can be used in all classes. However, they do not diminish the role of algebraic problem solving in teaching physics.

Drawing graphs expands the methodological possibilities of teaching. With the help of graphs, it is possible to clearly visualize the functional dependence between physical quantities. It is possible to determine whether the quantities are directly or inversely proportional to each other, how quickly one quantity increases or decreases with the change of another quantity, and when that quantity takes its largest and smallest values. Qrafik bu və ya digər hadisənin necə getməsinə təsvir etməyə imkan yaradır, hadisəni maddi tərəflərini görməyə imkan verir, şagirdlərin diqqətini öyrənilən hadisənin ən vacib yerlərinə yönəldir.

Reading graphs can be completed by writing a formula for a graph that describes a physical phenomenon.

In class VII, rectilinear constant velocity and rectilinear constant velocity movements are taught. Me-

mechanical movement is graphically described. The dependence between physical quantities is expressed with the help of the function:

- X(t) – change of coordinate over time,
- S(t) – change of path over time,
- v(t) – speed change over time,
- a(t) – change of momentum with time.

In rectilinear constant velocity motion of a material point, the path and coordinate is a linear function of time. The graphs of X(t) and S(t) make a certain angle with the time axis. Since the acceleration is zero, the graph of a(t) is a straight line on the time axis. The

graph of v(t) is a straight line parallel to the time axis – velocity is independent of time.

In rectilinear uniform motion, the graphs of x(t) and S(t) are parabola, quadratic dependence on time; if the arm of the parabola points up, the motion is uniform, if the arm of the parabola points down, the motion is uniform. Təcil zamana görə dəyişmir, a(t) – qrafiki zaman oxuna paralel düz xəttidir.

v(t) is a straight line whose graph passes through the coordinate origin (or a certain initial value of the velocity). This line slopes up or down as the speed increases or decreases.

The following types of graphical problems can be shown:

Problem 1. The graphs characterizing the movement of the pedestrian are given in the picture. Illustrate this motion using both graphs.

Answer: graph of change of coordinate is given in figure a). From here it can be seen that the pedestrian has returned to the place where he started his movement. Figure b) shows the road map. It is possible to

1. **Reading graphs**, gathering information about the physical phenomena shown by examining the graph dependence in the problem.

determine the path of the pedestrian to point C along the ordinate axis. In the graph, segments OA and BC correspond to uniform motion. AB is a stop. In both cases, the speed of movement is the same. This is determined by the inclination of the lines OA and BC to the time axis.

Problem 2. "Read" the solidification graph of the liquid. The temperature-time graph of the water placed in the refrigerator's freezer is given.

Discuss the result:

- What does AB, BC and CD represent in the graph?

- Why doesn't the temperature change in BC?

2. **Construction of graphs.** The graphs are built with the help of the tabular values obtained as a result of the calculation.

Problem 1. One end of the rope is attached to a nail, and the other end is attached to a dynamometer. The nail is caught on the left edge of the magnet. Then it is slowly moved along the magnet. At this time, how will the traction force of the dynamometer change.

Make a graph of the dependence of that force on the coordinate of the nail in your notebook. Take the position of the left edge where the nail stands as the coordinate origin.

4. Problems expressed by a conditional graph.

Problem 1. Based on the given picture, find the displacement and the path traveled on the time-dependent graph of the projection of the velocity of the object. At $t=3$ seconds, the velocity of the object has changed its direction.

$s_1 = \frac{a_1 b_1}{2}$ - $t=3$ per second, $s_2 = \frac{a_2 b_2}{2}$ - $t=1$ the area of the triangle if equal to the second;

$$a_1 = \Delta t_1 = 3 \text{ s}; b_1 = v_{1x} = 30 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$$

$$a_2 = \Delta t_2 = 1 \text{ s}; b_2 = v_{2x} = \frac{10 \text{ m}}{\text{s}}$$

According to the movement of the object in the direction of the x axis, the displacement vector $\Delta r_1 > 0$, ($v_{1x} > 0$). the object moves against the x -axis, $\Delta r_2 < 0$, ($\Delta v_{2x} < 0$).

Then : $\Delta r_{1x} = s_1 = 45 \text{ m}$; $\Delta r_{2x} = s_2 = -5 \text{ m}$

Displacement of the object $\Delta r_x = 40 \text{ m}$; distans traveled $S=50 \text{ m-dir}$.

1.2.Steps of solving graphic problems.

Graphical issues are mainly solved in the following stages:

- to determine the dependence between quantities;
- show quantities using a scale (abscissa, ordinate, area, etc.);
- construct a graph based on the values in the given table.

One of the problem solving methods is the algorithmic method. By solving many problems, students feel a rule in the solution system. Series of issues are resolved by this rule.

Algorithm for solving problems related to the determination of the type of movement of the object.

1. Determine the physical quantity on the vertical and horizontal axes of the graph.
2. Determine the units of measurement of physical quantities, if necessary, express the units of measurement in basic units of measurement.
3. Recall the equations of $x(t)$ or $S(t)$ in constant-velocity and constant-velocity motion (rectilinearly accelerating, rectilinearly decelerating), how is this dependence (linear or parabolic), i.e.
 - uniform motion: $x = x_0 + vt$ – straight line
 - smooth motion: $x = x_0 + v_0 t + \frac{at^2}{2}$ – arm of parabola

$$S_x = x - x_0$$

In rectilinear uniform motion, the acceleration vector is equal to zero: $a=0$

In rectilinear uniform motion, the acceleration vector is a constant quantity: $a=\text{const}$ Acceleration in rectilinear uniform motion:

$$a = \frac{v - v_0}{t - t_0}$$

Speed in rectilinear uniform motion:

$$v_x = \frac{S_x}{t}$$

Velocity in rectilinear uniform motion:

$$v = v_0 + a(t - t_0)$$

4. Determine the type of motion: uniform speed, uniform acceleration or uniform deceleration.

Problem. Which graph shown in the figure (figure 1) correctly describes the time dependence of the velocity projection during uniform motion of a material point ($v_{0x} \neq 0$)?

Velocity projection during uniform motion: $v_x = v_{0x} + a_x t$ is in the form of. The graph is a straight line, the v_x axis starts from a certain point ($v_{0x} \neq 0$); the

tangent of the angle formed by the graph with the t-axis gives the instant $a_x \neq 0$. The sought graph corresponds to b.

Problem 2. Define as a graph:

1. Displacement projection in the first 4 sec.

2. The path taken during that time

a) $\Delta t = t_2 - t_1 = 4 \text{ sec}$ (during the first 4 seconds) the projection of the displacement vector is calculated as the area of the figure formed by the abscissa

axis of the graph (dashed area). Projection of the displacement vector as the object moves in the opposite direction of the x-axis

b) $\Delta r_x < 0 = -S = -12m$

Since the path is $S > 0$, $S = 12m$.

c) $s = \frac{ab}{2}$ the area of the triangle is calculated. $a = \Delta t = 4 \text{ sec.}; b = v_x = 15 \text{ m/sec}$

Projection of the displacement vector $\Delta r_x > 0$ so that the object moves in the direction of the OX axis ($v_x > 0$). Then $\Delta r_x = 30m, S = 30m$.

Algorithm for solving graphical problems.

1. To write the short condition of the problem by expressing the quantities in the BS system of units.

2. Carefully look at the coordinate axes (ordinate, abscissa). To determine the graph, which function is given: $a=a(t), v = v(t), S=S(t), v \text{ y} a x = x(t)$.

3. Determine the type of movement according to the graph.

4. Write equations according to the conditions of the problem:

$a_x = a_x(t), v_x = v_x(t), S_x = S_x(t) \text{ y} a x = x(t)$

5. To calculate by writing the prices instead.

t, san	1	2	3	4	5
x, m	8	18	31	48	70

Problem. The equation of motion of a material point is given as follows: $x=4+3t+2t^2$. You need to fill in the following table:

According to the values in the table, the time dependence graph of the coordinate will be as follows:

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